

Studies on Thiazolidinones. Part-XIV : Synthesis of 3,3'-Bisthiazolidinones and 2,2-Disubstituted Thiazolidinones from Azomethines

(Miss) J. SAHU, T. K. SAHU, S. K. NAIK and A. NAYAK

Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Sambalpur-768 017

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Several new 3,3'-bisthiazolidinones (III) and 2,2-disubstituted thiazolidinones (VIII) have been synthesised by the cycloadditive dehydration of thioglycolic acid to the azomethine derivatives (II) and (VII) prepared from the aliphatic diamines and heterocyclic monoamines, respectively. The structure of the compounds have been confirmed from the spectral data and elemental analysis. The fungicidal and bactericidal activities of the compounds have also been evaluated.

THE synthesis of *bis*(2-amino-4-thiazolidinone) and several of its higher homologues (I) have been reported by us¹ in which thiazolidinone moieties were linked through the imino nitrogen at position-2. These were obtained from *bis*thioureas of the diamine with monochloroacetic acid. In our present communication a new series of thiazolidinones (III) in which the two thiazolidinone moieties are linked to each other through the nitrogen atom of the ring at position 3 have been prepared by two independent methods from the same diamines. In the first method the diarylidene derivatives (II) prepared from the diamines with aldehydes in the medium of alcohol and piperidine were reacted with thioglycolic acid in the medium of toluene or benzene. The thiol acid underwent Michael addition followed by dehydrative cyclisation. The reaction was carried out using Dean and Stark apparatus. In the second method a mixture of diamine and aldehyde was reacted together and thioglycolic acid was added without isolating the intermediate. The yields of thiazolidinone by both the methods were found to be nearly the same.

The ir spectra of the *bis*thiazolidinone (III; $n=2$, $R=C_6H_5$) prepared from ethylenediamine furnished strong peaks at 2930 and 1660 cm^{-1} corresponding to methylene and carbonyl absorptions, respectively whereas in the case of its benzylidene derivative (IV; $n=2$, $R=C_6H_5$) the bathochromic shift in the carbonyl absorption occurs (1650 cm^{-1}) due to its conjugation. The analytical data of the arylidene derivative (IV) indicate that only one thiazolidinone ring underwent condensation with aldehydes at C_2 position as reported by us¹ as well as other workers² in similar types of compounds. The arylidene compounds were soluble in alkali and reprecipitated unchanged after acidification, indicating one methylene group intact. The benzylidene compounds also underwent coupling with diazotised sulphanilamide indicating the presence of active hydrogen. The dibromo derivatives (V) of the arylidene thiazolidinone were also prepared in the acetic acid medium with a view to evaluating their antimicrobial activities.

The second series of thiazolidinones (VIII) were prepared by the same process starting from the azomethine compounds (VII), obtained from ketones and 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxa/thiadiazoles. The azomethine compounds were prepared by the KOH treatment of the α -cyanoamines (VI) prepared by the reaction of heterocyclic amines, acetophenone and KCN (Scheme 1). Several attempts to prepare the arylidene thiazolidinones from VIII failed in our hands.

Bactericidal activities :

Bactericidal activities of the compounds were evaluated by agar plate technique using *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*. The chlorothiazolidinones have feeble activities (Table 1).

TABLE 1—THIAZOLIDINONES (III)

n	R	m.p.	%Sulphur Found/(Calcd.)	SA	BS
0	Phenyl	—	—	—	+
	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	170	15.16 (15.88)	+	—
	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	208	15.17 (15.05)	+	+
2	Phenyl	208	16.50 (16.66)	—	—
	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	129	—	+	—
	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	141	14.28 (14.12)	+	2+
3	Phenyl	127	16.28 (16.07)	—	—
	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	136	13.74 (13.96)	—	—
	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	201	—	+	+
4	Phenyl	133	15.40 (15.53)	—	—
	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	140	—	—	+
	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	160	13.15 (13.36)	—	—

Yields varies from 30-75% ; SA = *S. aureus* ; BS = *B. subtilis*.
+ = zone size 6-8 mm ; 2+ = zone size 9-14 mm ; — = inactive

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The IR spectra of the compounds were taken on KBr disc in Perkin Elmer Model 293 spectrophotometer.

Bis(2-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone-3-yl) (III ; R = C₆H₅-): A mixture of benzaldehyde (1.06 g ; 0.01 M) and hydrazine (0.5 ml) in dry benzene (50 ml) was refluxed using a water separator. After separation of theoretical amount of water it was treated with thioglycolic acid (1 ml ; 0.01 M) and further refluxed for 6 hr. The solvent removed and the yellow residue was washed with Na₂CO₃ solution and finally with water. After drying it was crystallised from ethyl alcohol as pale yellow flakes, m.p. 130°, yield 0.8 g (5%). (Found : S, 18.12. C₁₈H₁₆N₂O₂S₂ requires S, 18.07%). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) : 2950 (—CH₂—stretch), 1690 (C=O).

The same compound was also prepared from the dibenzylidene derivative of hydrazine (0.4 g) (II ; n=0, R=C₆H₅) of m.p. 91° and thioglycolic acid (0.4 g) in the medium of toluene using a water separator, m.p. and mixed m.p. 130°.

1,2-Bis(2-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone-3-yl) ethane (III ; n=2, R=C₆H₅-): This was prepared from ethylene diamine (0.7 ml), benzaldehyde (2.2 g) and thioglycolic acid (2 g) by following the general procedure and finally isolated as colourless needles, m.p. 208°.

The same compound was also obtained by the reaction of dibenzylidene derivative of ethylene diamine (m.p. 55°) and thioglycolic acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 208°. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) : 2930 (—CH₂—stretch), 1660 (C=O).

Monobenzylidene derivative from III: A mixture of benzaldehyde (1.06 g ; 0.01 M), thiazolidinone (0.18 g ; 0.005 M) and fused sodium acetate (0.1 g) in glacial acetic acid (3 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. The yellow solution was poured into crushed ice and the pale yellow solid obtained was filtered off, washed thoroughly with cold water, dried and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 142° ; yield 45%. (Found : S, 14.26. C₂₅H₁₈N₂O₂S₂ requires S, 14.48%). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) : 2930 (—CH₂—stretch), 1650 (C=O). The m.p.s of the monobenzylidene derivatives of the other *bisthiazolidinones* (III ; n=2, 3 and 4) prepared by the above procedure are 184, 150 and 104°, respectively.

Dibromo derivatives from IV: A solution of the monobenzylidene thiazolidinone in acetic acid was treated with bromine in acetic acid in cold. The mixture was kept overnight and the vermilion coloured solid separated was washed with ether and finally dried in air. The melting points of the dibromoderivatives (V ; n=0, 2 and 3) are all more than 250°.

2-Phenyl-2-methyl-3-(1,3,4-thiadiazolyl-2)-4-thiazolidinone (VIII ; φ = 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl-2): A suspension of acetophenone (1.2 g) and KCN (0.7 g) in water (25 ml) was taken in a conical flask. It was cooled in a ice bath and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added to have a clear solution. 2-Amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1.0 g) in rectified spirit (15 ml) was added and kept in the refrigerator overnight. The α-cyanoamine (VI) separated was filtered off. It was dissolved in a methanolic solution of KOH (1.2 g in 100 ml) and refluxed for 2 hr. After cooling it was diluted with water (150 ml) and extracted with benzene. The benzene solution was dried in anhydrous CaCl₂ and the solvent was removed. The pasty mass left was suspended in dry benzene (100 ml) and thioglycolic acid (0.5 g) was added and refluxed for nearly two days. The solvent was removed and the residue treated with NaHCO₃ solution, filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 129° ; yield 40% (0.6 g). (Found : S, 23.26. C₁₂H₁₁N₃OS₂ requires S, 23.10%). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) : 2900, 1650 (C=O).

The following 2,2-disubstituted thiazolidinones have been prepared by the above procedure : VIII.

(ϕ =5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl-2), crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 224° ; VIII (ϕ =5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl-2), crystallised from DMF, m.p. 217°.

The other thiazolidinones (III) prepared from the aliphatic diamines have been presented in Table I.

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